

A Literature Review of Perumpaadu Management in Siddha

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ABSTRACT

Perumpaadu, (Menorrhagia) is one of the commonest gynaecological complaints, affecting 10-15 % of the adult female population. It is an abnormal uterine bleeding (AUB) occurring at any age but the problem is common in woman over 35 years. It causes considerable morbidity. It can cause the patient to become anaemic. On the contrary patient develops the risk of cancer of reproductive organs [15]. Ancient and traditional medicines have been used to handle menorrhagia for many centuries. Our siddha system of medicine is very effective in treating such problems. This article reveals the treatment of menorrhagia according to their in siddha aspect.

KEYWORDS: Perumpaadu, AUB, Menorrhagia, etiology, Siddha treatment, Drug.

ARTICLE DETAILS

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INTRODUCTION

Menstrual irregularities is consider as a major problems in women in India. Females of reproductive age experience cycles of hormonal activity that repeat at about (one-month) 28 days intervals. This series of natural changes is termed as menstrual cycle. Any changes in this cycle is consider as an abnormal condition, for any underlying diseases^[1]. This can be corrected through diet, medication, etc., Menorrhagia is one of the AUB that can be managed and treated through Siddha medicines. Here menorrhagia is denoted as *perumpaadu* in siddha literatures. This article gives as a brief knowledge about herbals, metals and minerals and animal origins that is used for treating menorrhagia.

Definition: [15]

Menorrhagia (perumpaadu) is defined as cyclic bleeding at normal intervals; the bleeding is either excessive in amount (>80 ml) or duration or both.

Related terminology: [1]

Abnormal uterine bleeding (AUB) is used to describe any deviation from the normal menstrual cycle. The related terms are also given in siddha aspect:

i. Abarimidha perumpaadu

It is defined as excessive menstrual bleeding with regular or irregular interval and in normal duration of cycle.

ii. Adhama perumpaadu

It is defined as intercylic bleeding.

Etiology in modern aspect: [15] [17]

Menorrhagia is a symptom of some underlying pathology – organic or functional.

i. Organic

✚ Pelvic pathology:

- ✓ Fibroid uterus
- ✓ Adenomyosis
- ✓ Pelvic endometriosis
- ✓ IUCD in-utero
- ✓ Chronic tubo-ovarian mass
- ✓ Tubercular endometritis (early cases)
- ✓ Retroverted uterus – due to congestion
- ✓ Granulosa cell tumour of the ovary

✚ Systemic

- ✓ Liver dysfunction – failure to conjugate and thereby inactivates the oestrogens.
- ✓ Congestive cardiac failure
- ✓ Severe hypertension

✚ Endocrinal

- ✓ Hypothyroidism
- ✓ Hyperthyroidism

✚ Blood dyscrasias

- ✓ Idiopathic thrombocytopenic purpura

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- ✓ Leukaemia
- ✓ von Willebrand's disease
- ✚ Emotional upset

- Genital tuberculosis (starting stage)
- Endocrine disorders
- Psychiatric illness

II. Functional

Due to disturbed hypothalamo-pituitary-ovarian-endometrial axis.

Etiology in Siddha aspect: ^[1]

There are two major types of perumpaadu (menorrhagia):

1. Saatharana perumpaadu
2. Asaatharana perumpaadu

I. Saatharana perumpaadu:

- Fibroid uterus or uterine polyps
- Pelvic tumors

II. Asaatharana perumpaadu:

Based on the symptoms and age, it can be classified as

- Excessive bleeding in adolescent age
- Postpartum bleeding
- Postmenopausal bleeding in old age

According to siddha literature, Yugimuni classified perumpaadu into four types;

- ❖ Vadha perumpaadu
- ❖ Pitha perumpaadu
- ❖ Sethpa perumpaadu
- ❖ Thondha perumpaadu

Treatment:

Herbals in treating menorrhagia: ^{[4] [5]}

S.No.	Plants	Botanical name	Parts used
1.	Asogu	<i>Saraca asoca</i>	Bark
2.	Atimaduram	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>	Root
3.	Atti	<i>Ficus racemosa</i>	Milk, bark
4.	Avarai	<i>Cassia auriculata</i>	Flower
5.	Itti	<i>Ficus microcarpa</i>	Tender fruit
6.	Lavangappattai	<i>Cinnamomum verum</i>	Bark
7.	Odimaram	<i>Lannea coromandelica</i>	Bark
8.	Ganjah	<i>Cannabis sativa</i>	Whole plant
9.	Kattukodi	<i>Cocculus hirsutus</i>	Leaves, root
10.	Karungali	<i>Acacia catechu</i>	Pesin
11.	Kavizhtumbai	<i>Trichodesma indicum</i>	Leaves
12.	Kasa	<i>Memecylon umbellatum</i>	Root
13.	Pannaikkirai	<i>Celosia argentea</i>	Flower
14.	Sengkiraitandu	<i>Amaranthus gangeticus</i>	Stem, green leaf, root
15.	Kizhkai nelli	<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i>	Root
16.	Kungiliyam	<i>Shorea robusta</i>	Pesin
17.	Kothumai	<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	Kothumai kanghee
18.	Sathikkai	<i>Myristica fragrans</i>	Unripen fruit
19.	Chaya maram	<i>Caesalpinia sappan</i>	Wooden pegs
20.	Chemparattai	<i>Hibiscus rosasinensis</i>	Leaves, flower, root

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21.	Chempai	<i>Sesbania sesban</i>	Seeds
22.	Thipilli	<i>Piper longum</i>	Unripen fruit, rice
23.	Thenku maram	<i>Cocus nucifera</i>	Root
24.	Thettran	<i>Strychnos potatorum</i>	Root
25.	Naval	<i>Syzygium cumini</i>	Bark
26.	Nilappusini	<i>Ipomoea mauritiana</i>	Tuber
27.	Nirmulli	<i>Hygrophila auriculata</i>	Seeds
28.	Nettlingam	<i>Polyalthia longifolia</i>	Bark
29.	Neithar kizhangu	<i>Nymphaea pubescens</i>	Flower
30.	Nel	<i>Oryza sativa</i>	Rice
31.	Nelli	<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i>	Leaves, flower, root, bark, unripen fruit, seed
32.	Pannimonthan kizhangu	<i>Trapa natans</i>	Seeds
33.	Chiru peelai	<i>Aerva lanata</i>	Whole plant
34.	Punaikkali	<i>Mucuna pruriens</i>	Seed
35.	Mantharai	<i>Bauhinia purpurea</i>	Flower
36.	Ma	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Seed, pesin
37.	Machikkai	<i>Quercus infectoria</i>	Unripen fruit
38.	Modagavalli	<i>Sterculia foetida</i>	Bark
39.	Valuzhuvai	<i>Celastrus paniculatus</i>	Seeds
40.	Vazhai	<i>Musa paradisiaca</i>	Flower
41.	Vilamaram	<i>Limonia acidissima</i>	Pesin
42.	Vellilothram	<i>Symplocos racemosa</i>	Bark, stem

Metals and minerals: [3]

	MEDICINES	DOSAGE	ADJUVANT
<input type="checkbox"/>	Iyarpapam	» ½-1 Kundri	Honey/ ghee
<input type="checkbox"/>	Iyanaaga parpam	» ½-1 Kundri	Cow's milk
<input type="checkbox"/>	Karuvanga parpam	» ½-1 Kundri	Alovera juice
<input type="checkbox"/>	Kandha parpam	» ½-1 Kundri	Milagu thailam
<input type="checkbox"/>	Naga parpam	» ½-1 Kundri	Urine (human)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vanga parpam	» ½-1 Kundri	Kadukilai juice
<input type="checkbox"/>	Velli parpam	» ½-1 Kundri	Cow's milk
<input type="checkbox"/>	Muthu parpam	» ½-1 Kundri	Warm water
<input type="checkbox"/>	Kavikkal chendooram	» 3 Kundri	Jaggery
<input type="checkbox"/>	Senkal kittam	» ½ Varagan	Jaggery
<input type="checkbox"/>	Sangu parpam	» ½-1 Kundri	Nandhiyavata juice

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□	Uppu parpam	» ½-1 Kundri	Warm water
□	Cheenakaram	» ½-1 Kundri	Milk
□	Padikara chendooram	» 1-2 Kundri	Butter/ghee
□	Padiga linga thuvar	» 3-5 Kundri	Butter/ghee
□	Venkaram	» 2½-7½ Kundri	-
□	Navamani – neelam	» ¼-1 Kundri	Honey
□	Pavazha parpam	» ½-1 Kundri	Honey

Named preparations:

Chooranam:

- ❖ Kombarakku chooranam ^[3]
- ❖ Maruthampattai chooranam ^[4]
- ❖ Raja elathi chooranam ^[9]
- ❖ Elathi chooranam ^[7]

Parpam:

- ❖ Poora parpam ^[11]

Chendooram:

- ❖ Unani chendooram ^[9]
- ❖ Karuvanga chendooram ^[10]

Leghiyam:

- ❖ Kungumam poo leghiyam ^[8]
- ❖ Maga aavarampattai leghiyam ^[8]
- ❖ Kasakasa leghiyam ^[2]

Other medicines:

- ❖ Manikkam kirudham ^[13]
- ❖ Sathavari Elagam ^[13]
- ❖ Maruthampattai Elagam ^[4]
- ❖ Vaazhai vadagam ^[16]
- ❖ Naval nei ^[10]

- ❖ Thadhu busti leghiyam ^[10]
- ❖ Paal leghiyam ^[6]

Nei:

- ❖ Sathavari nei ^[13]
- ❖ Venpoosani nei ^[12]
- ❖ Bramiya nivarana nei ^[6]
- ❖ Maha mega nei ^[6]
- ❖ Avarai nei ^[10]

Thailam:

- ❖ Asai thailam (ext) ^[2]
- ❖ Kizhanelli thailam (ext) ^[4]
- ❖ Vellai thailam ^[6]
- ❖ Kandhaga thailam ^[11]
- ❖ Eravelchinni ennai ^[6]
- ❖ Agathiyar sanjeevi ennai ^[11]

- ❖ Rathakasa mezhu ^[6]
- ❖ Maga kodusuli ^[6]
- ❖ Murunga erkku manapagu ^[14]
- ❖ Udhumparathi kasaya ^[7]

General hematonics to perumpaadu: ^[3]

- Iya bringuraja paanidham
- Karisalai karpam

- Thiriloga chendooram
- Egku chendooram
- Kandha chendooram
- Thandavala chendooram
- Mandura chendooram
- Sidha manduram
- Maha manduram
- Thirikadugu manduram
- Narayana manduram
- Mandura mathirai

- Iya jambeera karpam
- Iya chendooram

- Annabaethi chendooram
- Sangu parpam
- Arumuga chendooram
- Velli chendooram
- Thanga chendooram
- Iya parpam
- Kandha parpam
- Velli parpam
- Iya naga parpam

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